

US COVID19 DATA & FORECAST June 17h, 2020

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● Total cases

● Verhulst forecast of total cases

US COVID19 DATA & FORECAST June 17h, 2020

● Total deaths

● Verhulst forecast of total deaths

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● Total deaths

● Verhulst forecast of total deaths